

Imagining alternative futures for the Dutch poultry industry

Citation for published version (APA):

Smulders, B., Valkenburg, R., Markus, A., & Romme, A. G. L. (2025). Imagining alternative futures for the Dutch poultry industry. *Futures*, 166, Article 103519. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2024.103519>

Document license:

CC BY

DOI:

[10.1016/j.futures.2024.103519](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2024.103519)

Document status and date:

Published: 01/02/2025

Document Version:

Publisher's PDF, also known as Version of Record (includes final page, issue and volume numbers)

Please check the document version of this publication:

- A submitted manuscript is the version of the article upon submission and before peer-review. There can be important differences between the submitted version and the official published version of record. People interested in the research are advised to contact the author for the final version of the publication, or visit the DOI to the publisher's website.
- The final author version and the galley proof are versions of the publication after peer review.
- The final published version features the final layout of the paper including the volume, issue and page numbers.

[Link to publication](#)

General rights

Copyright and moral rights for the publications made accessible in the public portal are retained by the authors and/or other copyright owners and it is a condition of accessing publications that users recognise and abide by the legal requirements associated with these rights.

- Users may download and print one copy of any publication from the public portal for the purpose of private study or research.
- You may not further distribute the material or use it for any profit-making activity or commercial gain
- You may freely distribute the URL identifying the publication in the public portal.

If the publication is distributed under the terms of Article 25fa of the Dutch Copyright Act, indicated by the "Taverne" license above, please follow below link for the End User Agreement:

www.tue.nl/taverne

Take down policy

If you believe that this document breaches copyright please contact us at:

openaccess@tue.nl

providing details and we will investigate your claim.

Imagining alternative futures for the Dutch poultry industry

Britt Smulders^{*}, Rianne Valkenburg, Arjan Markus, Georges Romme

Department of Industrial Engineering and Innovation Sciences, Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, Netherlands

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Future images
Opportunity space
Sustainable transformation
Poultry industry
Agriculture

ABSTRACT

In their quest for sustainable transformation, agricultural industries need to move beyond product and service innovation as well as rivalry between actors toward reconfiguring production and consumption systems. In mature industries like agriculture, envisioning alternatives that require systemic innovation is challenging due to the dominance of existing systems. This study constructs future images, as design tools, to expand the opportunity space for sustainable transformation. Focusing on the Dutch poultry industry, we conducted futures interviews to identify and structure drivers of change and use these to construct future images by identifying values-based themes. We constructed and visualized six coherent future images depicting alternative contexts for this industry: ‘zero-emission policy agenda,’ ‘farmers as entrepreneurial innovators,’ ‘collaborative ecosystem,’ ‘retail as an orchestrator,’ ‘happy animals, healthy humans,’ and ‘living labs in the knowledge economy.’ We discuss how these futures expand the opportunity space for novel production and consumption systems, drawing on distinct sustainability conceptualizations and different actors.

1. Introduction

The need to transform agricultural industries’ systems of production and consumption to more sustainable alternatives has been highlighted in multiple calls (European Environment Agency, 2015; European Commission, 2019; 2020). Agricultural industries contribute to and face major environmental, economic, and social sustainability challenges (De Olde, Linden, Bolhaar, & Boer, 2020), including resource scarcity, biodiversity loss, climate change, emissions, animal welfare, pesticide use, and food quality and quantity (European Environment Agency, 2015). Policymakers, consumers, and farmers recognize the necessity for systemic change arising from these pressures, as reflected in evolving policy initiatives, changing consumer demand, and farmers’ growing financial difficulties. However, current sustainability interventions often focus on alternatives that are simple to envision, but also limited in their capacity for driving systemic change (Dorninger et al., 2020).

This article focuses on the Dutch poultry industry, a mature agricultural industry. In Europe, the demand for poultry meat and eggs is expected to grow, which will increase production (EC, 2019). This growth is partly due to the protein transition, where poultry products are replacing other animal proteins because they are affordable and convenient, are perceived as healthy, and have comparatively lower emissions (EC, 2019). According to the EU Agricultural Outlook (EC, 2019), poultry meat production is projected to rise to 16.5 million tons (a 5 % increase from 2019), and the consumption egg market is expected to reach 7.6 million tons (an 8 % increase from 2019). The Netherlands is among the top EU producers and exporters of poultry products, accounting for 6 % of the EU’s

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: b.smulders@tue.nl (B. Smulders), a.c.valkenburg@tue.nl (R. Valkenburg), a.markus@tue.nl (A. Markus), a.g.l.romme@tue.nl (G. Romme).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2024.103519>

Received 12 April 2024; Received in revised form 11 October 2024; Accepted 25 November 2024

Available online 28 November 2024

0016-3287/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

poultry meat (850 kilotons) and 6 % of its consumption and hatching eggs (525 kilotons) (European Commission, 2024a; 2024b). Like many other agricultural industries, the Dutch poultry industry has taken various sustainability initiatives, mainly targeting efficiency and optimization instead of fundamental changes in its production and consumption system.

To create new configurations of this production and consumption system, an essential first step is to envision alternatives (Kuhmonen, 2017), which is particularly challenging in mature industries due to the interdependencies between various subsystems (Kuhmonen & Kuhmonen, 2015). Previous foresight studies in agriculture have therefore explored scenarios to understand the interdependencies, uncertainties, potential responses to different pressures and interventions, and potential effects of drivers of change (Garnett et al., 2023; Shaaban et al., 2023; Sundbo, 2016). Recent research emphasizes that future images are more important than scenarios in addressing sustainability issues, as these aid in setting agendas, understanding future choices, and fostering innovation (Beers et al., 2010; Kuhmonen, 2017). In this respect, future images depict states of development rather than trajectories, capturing attention and mobilizing action (Beers et al., 2010). As such, this broader body of work on futures suggests that future images can be used as design tools for reflection, to inspire innovation and generate new development directions (De Smedt, Borch, & Fuller, 2013; Ko & Yang, 2023; Kuhmonen & Kuhmonen, 2015; Minkinen, Auffermann, & Ahokas, 2019).

This paper seeks to envision and create future images of alternative socio-technical contexts of the Dutch poultry industry that enlarge the opportunity space for potential reconfigurations of its production and consumption system. We argue that socio-technical contexts form the opportunity space for system-level innovation. By developing future images of such contexts, one can provide insight into alternative directions for development. Understanding how specific drivers of change might open different opportunity spaces, thereby guiding innovation in different directions, is crucial. For instance, current sustainability policies in The Netherlands seek to reduce emissions as an important goal (NVP & LTO, 2023), while other potential paths remain unexplored.

Our research question therefore is: *How, if at all, do incumbent actors envision future states of the Dutch poultry industry's production and consumption system, and in which directions?* To answer this, we identify drivers of change and create future images of alternative socio-technical contexts. We conducted 13 interviews with various experts in the Dutch poultry industry and value chain, performed a content analysis, and synthesized the results to construct future images, and then collaborated with an artist to co-create visual images. In our discussion, we explore these futures' opportunity spaces for reconfiguring the production and consumption system. This study contributes to the literature on future images by exploring their role as a design tool for innovation, highlighting alternative socio-technical contexts as spaces for innovation.

The paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we present the conceptual framework by describing how socio-technical contexts can be conceptualized as opportunity spaces for creating future images. The third section introduces the Dutch poultry industry and its path-dependent characteristics. The fourth section describes the data collection and analysis methods. Subsequently, we present the results in section five, discuss the main findings in section six, and conclude the argument in the final section.

2. Background

2.1. Socio-technical contexts as opportunity spaces

Social systems evolve in more complex ways than purely technical systems, due to the interaction between human agency and the environment. In this respect, the so-called path creation perspective emphasizes proactively shaping opportunities (Garud, Kumaraswamy, & Karnøe, 2010) by expanding the opportunity space (Jing & Benner, 2016). The opportunity space represents the 'perceived range of available options for variance by embedded actors, which can provide possibilities for courses of change actions' (adapted from Kornish & Ulrich, 2011 in Jing & Benner, 2016), which provides actors with varying resources and possibilities that influence decision-making (Jing & Benner, 2016).

In mature industries, the dominant design shapes actors' views, necessitating active efforts to envision system change (Kuhmonen & Kuhmonen, 2015). Sustainable transformation typically involves system innovation, focusing on reconfiguring the production and consumption systems, aligned with and embedded in a broader socio-technical context (Midgley & Lindhult, 2021; Truffer, Voß, & Konrad, 2008). However, in mature industries, most change tends to occur at the level of new products and services, or competition between firms (Adner, 2017), which are rather straightforward to envision but also limited in driving systemic transformation (Dorninger et al., 2020). For instance, in the Dutch poultry industry, organic production and direct-to-consumer services have been introduced but remain marginal compared to the dominant system of large incumbents (Berntsen, Menkveld, & Leguijt, 2021). Similar patterns are observed in other agricultural industries (Hörisch, 2018; Kuhmonen, 2017).

We argue that analyzing alternative socio-technical contexts may expand the opportunity space, by creating new directions for sustainable transformation of the existing production and consumption systems. This involves anticipating and envisioning changes in policy and regulations, socio-cultural traditions, infrastructure, industry and production, technology, users and markets, and societal and environmental effects caused by or addressed by industry practices (for an overview, see: Geels, 2002). We conceive of such analysis as a form of projectivity, that is, imagining alternative futures to better understand potential futures and inform transformative actions that can transcend current constraints (Emirbayer & Mische, 1998).

2.2. Future images

Futures research employs plausible, possible, and desirable futures to anticipate uncertainties, assess risks, evaluate feasibility, persuade stakeholders, and stimulate innovation (De Smedt et al., 2013; Rohrbeck and Gemünden, 2011; Sarpong, Maclean, & Alexander, 2013; Tsoukas & Shepherd, 2004). It addresses sustainability challenges by navigating ambiguous and unknown territory,

leveraging the transformative capacity of futures to construct path-breaking futures (Augustine, Soderstrom, Milner, & Weber, 2019). To this end, scholars studying futures highlight the use of future images to support efforts to envision, structure, and compare divergent possibilities through extracting alternatives in a state space (Beers et al., 2010; Kuhmonen, 2017).

Unlike scenarios that narrate hypothetical sequences of events from present to future (Schwartz, 1996), future images are ‘snapshots’ of possible or desirable futures – specific, impressionistic descriptions of future states (Bell & Mau, 1971; Jarva, 2014; Kuhmonen, 2017). These images are grounded in beliefs, expectations, opinions, values, hopes, fears (Rubin, 2013), and ongoing and future developments (Jokinen et al. 2022). While scenarios rely on factual data, future images integrate structural knowledge with imaginative elements (Nygrén, Tapio, & Qi, 2017); in other words, future images are formed from knowledge and enriched by imagination (Marjamaa & Mäkelä, 2022).

Recent work on future images includes a few studies on food and agriculture (Beers et al., 2010; Kuhmonen, 2017; Vinnari & Tapio, 2009). For instance, Vinnari and Tapio (2009) developed five future images to illustrate diverse consumer and expert views on meat consumption by 2030. Beers et al. (2010) examined several Dutch agricultural transition projects, to identify future images and their visualization as key to fostering innovation. Moreover, Kuhmonen (2017) analyzed four future images of Finland’s food system: a short food chain for economic sustainability, a green food chain for environmental sustainability, a fair food chain for social sustainability, and a genuine food chain for cultural sustainability.

Broader research on future images has explored expert opinions on futures (Nygrén et al., 2017), their role in assessing commitments, actions, and consequences (Luoma, Penttinen, Tapio, & Toppinen, 2022), reflections on achieving sustainability goals (Marjamaa & Mäkelä, 2022), target setting for sustainability actions (Jokinen et al., 2022), and potential transition paths (Mäkelä, Parkkinen, Lyytimäki, & Nygrén, 2020). Importantly, Kuhmonen and Kuhmonen (2015) argue that in fields with a dominant view on the future, such as mature industries, future images are a tool for social learning about agency and structure, which in turn makes it harder to dismiss diverse possibilities for development.

Overall, prior work emphasizes that future images are tools for exploring alternative futures in specific domains and recognizing that factors can be influenced (De Smedt et al., 2013; Kuhmonen & Kuhmonen, 2015). Rather than depicting the final outcomes to be realized, future images facilitate the emergence of opportunities in the present (Minkkinen et al., 2019). Several authors have thus called for more research on using futures as tools for stimulating innovation, focused on challenging current assumptions to expand possibilities and generate new paths (Ko & Yang, 2023; Minkkinen et al., 2019).

This paper responds to the latter call by using future images as design tools for expanding the opportunity space for sustainable transformation. More specifically, we identify the drivers of change behind these images and their interrelationships to enhance innovation opportunities (Vinnari & Tapio, 2009), as divergence occurs when drivers move in different directions (Saritas & Smith, 2011). We thus explore how attention to particular drivers of change in a future image might implicate specific opportunity spaces and direct innovation.

3. Existing production and consumption system in the Dutch poultry industry

The development of the Dutch poultry industry is typical for many agricultural industries. Since the 1960s, the industry has industrialized and modernized, shifting from small-holder production to large-scale, cost-efficient operations. The industry has faced criticism in subsequent decades, particularly regarding environmental impacts and animal welfare (Spoelstra, Groot Koerkamp, Bos, Elzen, & Leenstra, 2013). In the egg sector, the backlash against battery cages led to policies mandating minimum space for hens and introducing barn eggs in retail (Mollenhorst and De Boer, 2004; Spoelstra et al., 2013). The broiler sector modernized through increased exports, with the public debate on broiler welfare driving product differentiation toward fresh meat (Hin, Wagenaar, Van der Zijpp, & Van der Weijden, 2013; Zanders, 2015). Additionally, a poultry production rights system was introduced to meet EU emission regulations (Spoelstra et al., 2013).

Recent crises, policies, and NGO actions have prompted key industry actors to focus more on environmental impact, animal welfare, and quality. New standards like the ‘1 star better life’ certification at retailers reflect the increased NGO and market involvement in animal welfare developments (Beldman, et al., 2022). In the egg sector, the phase-out of battery cages in 2012 and enriched cages in 2021 led to the widespread adoption of alternative housing systems for poultry (Berntsen et al., 2021). Similarly, concerns about fast-growing broilers led to the introduction of slow-growing breeds (Zanders, 2015), resulting in more concept chicken, ‘better life,’ and organic offerings (Berntsen et al., 2021). Retail sales dominate the majority of domestic production and consumption, with exports also playing a significant role.

The Dutch poultry industry positions itself as a leader in sustainable production, with over 85 % of laying hens in free-range barns and over one-third of broilers being slow-growing breeds with extra living space (Berntsen et al., 2021). However, like other mature agricultural industries, it faces strong path dependencies that constrain opportunities for innovation. As a result, innovation activity primarily involves (developing) new products, services, and housing systems. This creates major dilemmas when improvements in animal welfare and social, environmental and financial sustainability do not align at the system level (Berntsen et al., 2021).

Four critical dependencies influence the potential futures of the production and consumption system. First, the system’s activities are spread across many highly *specialized organizations*, with certain players (e.g., retailers) taking on important coordinating roles. Second, relatively small and financially vulnerable farmers bear most production risks, operating as *independent entrepreneurs* in a system dominated by large incumbents. Third, the industry heavily depends on *policies and NGO actions that define sustainability* by, for example, targeting emissions and animal welfare. Fourth, the Dutch poultry industry and value chain are highly *globalized*, with major volumes of imports and exports. These four dependencies are essential in analyzing future images and the potential for agentic change.

4. Method

There is no universal research method for constructing future images, because it has to align with the specific topic and problem. This study aims to create future images of socio-technical contexts and explore how focusing on particular drivers of change can lead to innovation in specific directions. We develop future images through a four-step process, outlined in Fig. 1: (1) futures interviews, (2) content analysis, (3) creative synthesis, and (4) visualization. *Futures interviews* are used to identify relevant drivers of change and elements of futures. *Content analysis* serves to structure these drivers of change and elements of futures. *Creative synthesis* constructs the logic underlying the future images, and *visualization* creates impressionistic pictures of alternative socio-technical contexts.

4.1. Data collection using futures interviews

The research began with interviews with industry experts to identify drivers of change and futures elements. Future images can leverage experts' structural and social knowledge, experience, and imagination (Nygrén et al., 2017). Therefore, involving local stakeholders in futures exercises is crucial (Bourgeois & Sette, 2017). As such, all futures interviews were conducted with Dutch poultry industry experts. In this respect, expertise is a role attributed to individuals in the industry, rather than an inherent cognitive ability for foresight or imagination (Mauksch, von der Gracht, & Gordon, 2020). A peer nomination process thus facilitated the selection of experts, where initial field experts identified additional experts (Mauksch et al., 2020). The research team triangulated nominations with external indicators such as job type and position.

Expert participation largely drives the output of future images, and the research design therefore must limit biases. Kuhmonen and Kuhmonen (2015) identified three biases: perspective bias, normative bias, and directional bias. Perspective bias was mitigated by selecting experts with diverse viewpoints from various organizations within the industry, including public institutions, expertise centers, consultancies, and research institutes (see Table 1).

Normative bias was addressed by encouraging participants to share their hopes, desires, and fears for negative impacts across all dimensions of the socio-technical context (see Table 2). This approach challenged the experts' preferred futures and reduced the risk of producing projections only based on past experiences (Mische, 2009).

Directional bias can occur when experts focus too much on either top-down macro forces or bottom-up initiatives (Kuhmonen & Kuhmonen, 2015). To address this, we probed experts with key trends and asked about their relation to industry-level drivers of change. Key trends are macro-level forces driving societal change, while drivers of change are specific factors influenced by strategic actions (Saritas & Smith, 2011). Key trends are found in horizon scanning reports, typically compiled by strategists, consultancies, and policy analysts to outline societal developments (Spaniol & Rowland, 2022). To identify key trends for probing experts in the interviews, we reviewed an Oxfam horizon scanning report (Artuso & Guijt, 2020), which summarizes 22 megatrend reports to provide a comprehensive overview of key trends. These trends were categorized across dimensions of socio-technical contexts (Table 2) and cross-checked with two additional reports (European Environment Agency, 2015; Klein, Bansal, & Wohlers, 2017). The supplementary material provides an overview of the key trends used in the interviews. This approach encouraged experts to think beyond prevailing norms and determine the appropriate level of abstraction for the futures exercise, and thereby address the complexity of envisioning futures (Finn & Wylie, 2021).

In the futures interviews, experts were asked two critical questions for each context dimension (Table 2) regarding the future of the Dutch poultry industry: i) which, if any, of these trends relates most closely to the future of the industry from your perspective as an expert, and ii) considering this trend as a force of change, can you specify how you think (hope, desire, or fear) it can impact the industry? We gave interviewees a definition for each context dimension (see Table 2), showed proving statements with key trends, and asked the same two questions. Notably, interviewees were explicitly instructed that they were free to provide input beyond the probes provided or discuss multiple probes as they saw fit, which they regularly did. The interview questions and interview template with the future probes are included in the Appendix.

Fig. 1. Overview of steps.

Table 1
Overview of participants.

No. of experts	Organization	Area of expertise						
		Policy	Industry & Production	Infrastructure	Technology	Societal & Environmental effects	Socio-cultural traditions	Users & Markets
2	Expertise center	x	x	x	x	x		
3	University of applied sciences			x	x	x		
1	Environmental consultancy		x		x	x		
2	Universities			x	x	x		
2	Government	x						
1	Bank	x	x	x				x
1	Sector organization		x	x			x	x
1	NGO	x				x		x
N = 13								

Table 2
Overview and definition of socio-technical system dimensions, adapted from Geels (2002).

Dimensions of the socio-technical context	Description
<i>Policy and regulations</i>	Policy initiatives and regulations at different levels (EU/national/local/industry) that enable and constrain the industry
<i>Sociocultural traditions</i>	Meanings, values, and perceptions about industry practices by society
<i>Infrastructure</i>	Resources, capabilities, and infrastructure that support the industry
<i>Industry and production</i>	The supply side of the industry - key actors in creating value, supporting actors
<i>Technology</i>	Core technologies used, complementary technologies (perhaps not yet available)
<i>Users and Markets</i>	The demand side of the industry - Users' preferences, willingness to pay, customers
<i>Societal and environmental effects</i>	Societal and environmental effects caused or addressed by industry practices

During the interviews, experts shared their perspectives on the industry’s future and were continually asked to clarify their statements. Although the questions might seem simple, the continuous clarification resulted in rich narratives about the future of the Dutch poultry industry, covering all socio-technical context dimensions. Data saturation was reached after interviews with 13 experts, each lasting one hour. Similarly, previous studies showed that future images can be created with fewer interviews, as saturation in the material is achieved (Kuhmonen & Kuhmonen, 2015; Mäkelä et al., 2020).

4.2. Content analysis, creative synthesis, and visualization of future images

Content analysis was conducted on the transcribed interview data to structure drivers of change and elements of futures. We used Nvivo for the qualitative data analysis. One researcher first reviewed all transcripts, categorizing the data into dimensions of policy and regulations, sociocultural traditions, infrastructure, industry and production, technology, users and markets, and societal and environmental effects (Table 2). We then proceeded by creating main codes representing drivers of change within each category. For instance, within ‘societal and environmental effects,’ we coded sentences and expressions related to the societal and environmental effects caused or addressed by industry practices. After this initial coding, we re-analyzed the data to generate more specific secondary codes, highlighting differences and nuances. The research team then discussed and refined the primary and secondary codes, reducing

Fig. 2. Overview of creative synthesis method for constructing future narratives.

them to core words and phrases and reorganizing them as needed. This process resulted in four to six overarching drivers of change within each dimension, specified by more granular secondary codes. An overview of the resulting coding structure can be found in the [supplementary material](#).

The next step involved *creatively synthesizing* the logics of alternative contexts for the Dutch poultry industry. Constructing future images is a creative process grounded in formal analysis, but enhanced by disciplined imagination (Kuhmonen & Kuhmonen, 2015; Marjamaa & Mäkelä, 2022, see Weick, 1989), which we achieved through a creative synthesis process. Future images are value-laden depictions of alternative states (Beers et al., 2010). To inform our synthesis, we identified several themes in the data which indicate underlying values and sources of agency, such as policy initiatives, entrepreneurship, large corporations, or an ecosystem. These value-laden themes served to synthesize drivers of change across the context dimensions (Fig. 2). The rich narratives from the interview data were important for coherently synthesizing the drivers of change, adding discipline to the imaginative process. Through an iterative process, we further developed the future images, uncovering two additional value-laden themes related to the agency of animals and humans and the knowledge economy. This resulted in six coherent change logics leading to alternative socio-technical contexts for the Dutch poultry industry (see Table 3 for a detailed overview).

Based on these six logics, we constructed a textual image and visualized it to depict alternative socio-technical contexts of the Dutch poultry industry. Visualization of future images can prevent overly simplistic future images and grow awareness of the complexity of sustainability issues (Augustine et al., 2019; Beers et al., 2010). The initial textual version describes the changes resulting in an alternative state. Collaborating with a visual artist, we holistically depicted these future states. In this visualization process, distinctions had to be made between the image's 'foreground' and 'background', to indicate primary drivers as foundational for the alternative state and move secondary drivers to the background, which adds depth and richness to the exercise. The main challenge was to create impressionistic images of the future state, rather than just listing changes, which required that we had to concretize the specific consequences implied by the drivers of change.

The future images were validated in a follow-up workshop with six experts in the Dutch poultry industry. In these workshops, the experts extensively engaged with these future images (outlined in Table 3), to check whether and how they could relate to their various elements and subsequently used them to develop a wide variety of potential innovation directions for the Dutch poultry industry.

5. Results

This section describes the six images of alternative socio-technical systems of the Dutch poultry industry. We present these future images in text and with the corresponding visualization.

5.1. Future image: Zero-emission policy development

In 2050 in The Netherlands. Attention to the environment and reducing emissions to net zero are at the top of every national policy agenda. The environment and nature reserves have the full attention of policymakers who want to protect them from particle matter and other emissions. See Fig. 3 for an impression of this future image.

Consumers are using the sustainability label developed by the European Union to choose environmentally friendly products – increasing the demand for agricultural products with attention to their environmental impact. Sensors are used throughout the production process, including the agricultural system, to track environmental impacts. A data management system shows how changes in emissions are related to specific characteristics in the farming system and other parts of the production chain. For example, farmers can track in real time how a change in feed affects the emissions produced.

Many farmers see opportunities to innovate and create new business models around reducing CO₂, nitrate, and ammonia emissions. Other farmers are installing renewable energy sources, applying circular farming, reusing waste as feedstock, and processing products on the farm to reduce transportation.

Achieving zero emissions came at a cost to the industry. Stringent national regulations created an uneven playing field, making it difficult for farmers to compete in the export market. Less land is devoted to agriculture to protect natural reserves from particulates and other emissions. Two different types of production methods serve to reduce emissions. Some farmers focus on capturing emissions even at their large-scale production sites. Other farmers are part of a production chain led by a small number of large multinationals. In these production chains, heavy investments in research and development result in new production systems that minimize environmental impacts while maximizing yields.

5.2. Future image: Farmers as entrepreneurial innovators

In 2050 in The Netherlands. Consumers are more aware than ever of the impact of agriculture on the environment and animal welfare. In a diverse society, this has led to many different customer groups with specific needs and demands. Farmers have risen to the challenge and are listening closely to society to adapt to changing customer demands. This has led to the development of new concepts and niche products that push the boundaries of the industry. See Fig. 4 for an impression of the 'farmers as entrepreneurial innovators' future image.

Entrepreneurial farmers use increased consumer awareness to develop products that respond to increased animal welfare or environmental impact concerns and create profit through new value-creation mechanisms. Farmers are leading innovation by co-creating new concepts and products with industrial partners. They are in close contact with consumers and other organizations such as suppliers and NGOs.

Table 3
Summary of the logics of six future images.

<i>Logic of Future image</i>	Future image 1: Zero-emission policy agenda	Future image 2: Livestock farmers as entrepreneurial innovators	Future image 3: Collaborative ecosystem
Theme of logic			
<i>Agency perspective</i>	Policy development	Farmers	Collaborative ecosystem
<i>Values</i>	Attention to emissions	Entrepreneurship and innovation	Cooperation and fair organization
<i>Value-laden theme</i>	In 2050 there is zero-emission policy and regulation	In 2050 there is a diversity of concepts in response to a more diverse society	In 2050 there is an ecosystem based on fair cooperation and shared responsibility
Dimensions of logic			
<i>Policy and regulations</i>	Changing policy with attention to environmental goals	Changing role and attitude of government by using target-directed policies rather than means-directed	Changing industry-led policy reliant on market dynamics
<i>Socio-cultural traditions</i>	Innovativeness of sector	Entrepreneurship of farmers Changing dynamics in society related to closer contact between farmers and consumers and less separation in society could cause polarization and distrust Changing consumption patterns by new opportunities resulting from changing groups in society	Innovativeness of sector
<i>Infrastructure</i>	Influence of emission reduction at farm level	Changing relation to future workers and renewed appreciation of workers	Changing area layout related to increased urbanization
<i>Industry and production</i>	Influence of emission reduction resulting in chain consolidation New business models for environmental sustainability	New business models for financial sustainability	Globalized infrastructure related to import and export New production chain organization, related to collaboration New business model for sustainable production (environmental, social, financial)
<i>Technology</i>	Data management in the production chain related to emission reduction	Skill development	Digitalization for optimization, communication, and integration Digitalization and its downsides and effects on competition
<i>Users and markets</i>	Sustainability awareness resulting in desire for transparency of products and production	Niche markets with more concepts and quality marks Sustainability awareness resulting in demand for guaranteed animal welfare and sustainability Changing spending to high quality protein Consumption pattern with protein transition and new types of products	Sustainability awareness resulting in desire for transparency of products and production
<i>Societal and environmental effects</i>	Increasing societal attention to emission reduction Expanding the role of technology for emission reduction	Transition toward social and ecological indicators	Trade-offs between economic, ecological, and social sustainability
<i>Logic of Future image</i>	Future image 4: Retail as an orchestrator	Future image 5: Happy animals and healthy humans	Future image 6: Living labs in the knowledge economy
Theme of logic			
<i>Agency perspective</i>	Retail	Happy animal and healthy human	Knowledge economy
<i>Values</i>	Socio-ecological systems	Welfare and well-being	Export of knowledge and know-how
<i>Value-laden theme</i>	In 2050 our world food system is resilient	In 2050 production is animal friendly with impact on people and society	In 2050 the sector is a living lab for new developments
Dimensions of logic			
<i>Policy and regulations</i>	Changing government-led policy for a level playing field Changing government-led policy by translating EU policies to local contexts	Changing industry-led policy directed by NGOs Changing policy targeting animal welfare	Changing government-led policy with guiding vision for technology, sustainability, and animal welfare Changing government-led policy by considering differences between EU and other countries
<i>Socio-cultural traditions</i>	Changing consumption patterns of different groups and generations	Changing consumption patterns of different groups and generations Innovativeness of the sector	New opportunities resulting from a changing society
<i>Infrastructure</i>	Globalized infrastructure, local production and international conflicts Changing resources and impact of scarcity	Improve well-being of workers Changing area layout, related to avian influenza	Knowledge infrastructure Globalized infrastructure, related to import and export
<i>Industry and production</i>	Breaking down robust systems, resilient food systems related to fewer chemicals, circularity, self-sufficiency New production organization regarding resource use and circularity	New business models for animal welfare	New business model for sustainable production (environmental, social, financial)

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Logic of Future image	Future image 4: Retail as an orchestrator	Future image 5: Happy animals and healthy humans	Future image 6: Living labs in the knowledge economy
Technology	Alternative technologies	Alternative technologies Data management of the production chain related to monitoring animal welfare and health as well as transparency and tracking	Skill development Alternative technologies
Users and markets	Changing consumption patterns related to maximum carcass utilization and new types of products International market with import and export of products Sustainability awareness of consumers influenced by retail	Changing consumption patterns related to the protein transition, new types of products, and maximum carcass utilization Changing spending patterns to high quality protein Sustainability awareness influenced by social organizations and creating demand for guaranteed welfare and sustainability	Changing consumer spending to high-quality products Niche markets with concepts and quality marks
Societal and environmental effects	Trade-offs related to feed-food, integral food system, surface area, well-being and emissions	Societal debate led by NGOs and policies Societal pressures related to health and security concerns and social pressure for animal welfare and sustainability	Trade-offs for social, environmental, and financial sustainability

Fig. 3. Future image: zero-emission policy agenda.

Mutual understanding between farmers and the rest of society has led to a greater appreciation of the farming profession. More and more new young farmers are entering the market as agricultural education leads an innovation movement by teaching new digital skills and communication methods.

Quality is emphasized over quantity, focusing on high levels of welfare and protection of the environment. The focus of agriculture has shifted to the home market, and there is less production for export.

The government plays an important supporting role by implementing target policies instead of intervention-oriented policies, putting farmers in control of the innovation process. The farmers and their partners can now creatively explore how to reach sustainability targets. New investors have stepped up to enable the development of diverse value chains, each with its own methods and production process.

Fig. 4. Future image: livestock farmers as entrepreneurial innovators.

Fig. 5. Future image: collaborative ecosystem.

5.3. Future image: Collaborative ecosystem

In 2050 in The Netherlands. Organizations in the agriculture sector take responsibility for addressing trade-offs between finances, animal welfare, and the environment, which have plagued the industry for a long time. The central objective of the food system is a fair price for all actors while ensuring social and environmental sustainability. See Fig. 5 for an impression of the ‘collaborative ecosystem’ future.

Agriculture is organized in hubs where actors behave as collaborative ecosystems with close relations and exchanges. Organized as collaborative ecosystems, all actors – retail, food industry, slaughterhouses, and trade organizations – share responsibility and co-create environmental, social, and financial value.

Actors within the sector work closely together. Also, there is widespread cross-sectoral collaboration between farming systems – such as horticulture and animal husbandry. This approach not only decreases the total amount of space necessary for agriculture but also focuses on local production and use of the local environment and resources.

Regulatory institutions oversee these ecosystems to ensure a fair distribution of all value flows in the ecosystem. These institutions have replaced policymakers and NGOs in pushing regulations for sustainability in environmental, social, and financial terms. New technologies like blockchain, data sharing, and digital innovations support efforts to align and collaborate in the ecosystem by increasing efficiency and transparency in relations. Consumers benefit from increased data sharing and transparency, which shows precisely how the product is produced with all related impact characteristics of the production process. Data sharing in the ecosystem has impacted the independence of farmers as entrepreneurs because it requires long-term collaborations. Due to increased data sharing, an important point of attention for all actors is the notion of privacy and security, including who has access to what data.

5.4. Future image: Retail as an orchestrator

In 2050 in The Netherlands. Retailers, farmers, and production partners work together to create a resilient food system that sustainably produces food, withstands shocks, and ensures food accessibility for a growing world population. Retailers must balance available resources, food consumption, and consumption patterns in collaboration with farmers and production partners at local, regional, and international levels, which gives rise to design challenges. See Fig. 6 for a visual impression.

The use and availability of (sustainable) resources introduces tensions between decisions on a local and international level. Local policy initiatives promote local food production, reducing waste, using fewer chemicals, and small-scale production, focusing on self-sufficiency. However, consumers everywhere still consume animal products as they believe these provide essential micro- and macronutrients. This puts pressure on regional and global food system actors to produce enough to meet demand with the available resources.

Balancing consumption and demand with food production also introduces food security dilemmas. Locally and regionally, farmers

Fig. 6. Future image: retail as orchestrator.

have started to keep fewer animals at a higher welfare standard to create lower quantities, but higher-quality products are sold to consumers at a premium. At the same time, efforts to ensure global food security are underway to satisfy the increased demand for animal-based products for the growing world population by increasing intensive farming outside of Europe.

Consumption patterns of consumers imply that the import and export of products is still a concern. Product innovation has ensured that maximum carcass yield can be reached locally and regionally without needing to export products that are not consumed in other parts of the world. International agreements have been made to promote trade in sustainable and ethically produced food as consumers and retailers still demand various food types. The task of retailers, farmers, and production organizations is to work together toward resilient food systems through experimentation and transparency.

5.5. Future image: Happy animals and healthy humans

In 2050 in The Netherlands. Living conditions are good for both animals and people. Animal welfare is the top priority of farming systems, and as a result, it positively affects people and society. In Europe, we see two groups of customers. A large group focuses on the consumption of ‘high-quality’ products that prioritize animal welfare, even though these come at a premium. Another group of consumers is now vegetarian or plant-based but is still closely in touch with farmers. See Fig. 7 for a visual impression.

NGO campaigns continue to advocate for higher welfare standards, leading to an increase in startups and niche products that meet the demands of the European consumer. Production methods and business models have undergone significant changes, incorporating new breeds, additional space, new concepts emphasizing well-being, and even warranty contracts to ensure a better animal life. Other farms extended or transformed to plant-based farming products, as an alternative for vegan and vegetarian consumers.

Legislation on animal welfare is stringent and offers quality marks that define levels of animal well-being for consumers. The Council of Animal Affairs has even defined the value of animals as equal to that of humans. Regarding welfare and well-being, the working conditions of farm laborers are of high priority, and they focus on creating a stimulating and healthy working environment.

A sense of urgency is still felt regarding zoonoses and potential health risks, leading farms to relocate to rural areas removed from densely populated regions. In these rural areas, farms are essential in increasing biodiversity and keeping the ecosystem healthy. Insect hotels and keeping animals in forest-like areas are now, for instance, common practices on many farms.

Major investments are made in technology for animal-friendly food production. Additionally, a European infrastructure for data collection, analysis, and sharing has been completed to monitor the welfare of animals and humans. Blockchain is used extensively to create transparency in the production process. A recent article by farmers criticizes this data-intensive technology movement for increasing animal welfare by replacing human-animal interaction.

Fig. 7. Future image: happy animals and healthy humans.

5.6. Future image: Living labs in the knowledge economy

In 2050 in The Netherlands. In the heart of the agricultural industries, farmers, producers, suppliers, and retailers have come together to form a new value-creating initiative – a chain-encompassing food living lab. Their mission is simple: continuously innovating and experimenting with different production methods and business models to create sustainable food systems. Fig. 8 provides a visual impression of this future image.

Living lab partners develop robust yet adaptable systems tailored to specific wants, needs, and environments to keep the local business. After successful experimentation, these tailored systems are exported to new locations, providing solutions for local problems.

These living labs quickly became a way to create value through unique know-how. Their experimental approach to technological and business model innovation makes them highly competitive. In the living labs, organizations continuously focus on producing knowledge on the practical application of innovative farming systems, production systems, and business models. Pursuing knowledge and technological innovation supports a new era of exploration, funded with the help of investors closely involved with the living labs.

Consumers are drawn to the high-quality and innovative products that these living labs produce. However, not all are willing to pay the premium for sustainable products or choose to focus specifically on either welfare or the environment. Close investigation and connection with the market and consumers is a central task. Transferring these insights to other locations remains a challenge.

Local regulations are even more focused on stimulating the speed of innovation and the number of living labs. However, these strict legislations also limit the import and export of agricultural products, which has a detrimental effect on food availability and organizations in the industry. As the living labs continue to push boundaries and innovate, policymakers at the European level attempt to keep up in creating up-to-date legislation focused on animal welfare and the protection of the environment.

6. Discussion

In this study, we constructed future images of alternative socio-technical contexts as an opportunity space for systemic innovation in the Dutch poultry industry. We employed a four-step approach using futures interviews, content analysis, creative synthesis, and visualization to create impressionistic depictions of these contexts. This approach was instrumental in constructing six future images: ‘zero-emission policy agenda,’ ‘farmers as entrepreneurial innovators,’ ‘collaborative ecosystem,’ ‘retail as an orchestrator,’ ‘happy animals, healthy humans,’ and ‘living labs in the knowledge economy.’

Our study demonstrates how future images can be used as design tools to expand the opportunity space for systemic transformations toward sustainability. The socio-technical contexts depicted by the future images serve as divergent opportunity spaces, offering insights into the sustainable transformation options for the industry studied. Our results indicate that different values and

Fig. 8. Future image: living labs in the knowledge economy.

agencies give rise to distinct drivers for sustainable transformation, leading to depictions of alternative socio-technical contexts that are fundamentally different from the existing system. In this section, we discuss the extent to which the drivers for change and their interplay, as illustrated by the future images, create different opportunity spaces for sustainable transformation. Second, we also discuss how visualization affects the depiction and meaning of these drivers and how it encourages the use of futures as a design tool for innovation. Finally, we address various limitations of this study and suggest directions for future research.

6.1. Creating opportunity spaces for sustainable transformation

In the first future image ('zero-emission policy agenda') developed, the sustainability efforts focus on environmental sustainability with zero emissions through government policies and collaborative innovation by farmers and large corporations. This shows similarities to the poultry industry's current direction, with policy actions aiming to reduce emissions via technological innovation and decrease the number of animals. Our future image goes beyond these existing policies by highlighting the importance of large-scale research and development efforts on alternative production methods across the entire chain, which minimize environmental impacts while maximizing yield. Here, emission reduction in agriculture remains a primary goal of any foresight exercise (Prager & Wiebe, 2021).

The second image ('farmers as entrepreneurial innovators') envisions financial sustainability, driven by entrepreneurial farmers collaborating with producers and consumers. It leverages farmers' entrepreneurship to actively create value by catering to diverse consumer preferences, turning independent entrepreneurship from a vulnerability into a strength. Farmers take on new roles as co-creators with consumers and production partners, aligning with and beyond studies emphasizing direct producer-consumer interactions without retail intermediaries (Kuhmonen, 2017). Current developments in the industry also entail high-quality and small-scale production, but as a rather small portion of the market (Berntsen et al., 2021); the 'farmers as entrepreneurial innovators' image views the entire market as being driven by such concepts, moving away from an export-centric approach.

The third 'collaborative ecosystem' image emphasizes sustainable transformation by balancing financial, social, and ecological sustainability through collaborative actions among producers. It contrasts with the Dutch poultry industry's current specialization by promoting fundamental collaboration and shared responsibility to tackle sustainability issues and ensure fair pricing. The current activities, which are organizationally and geographically dispersed, would transform to a collaborative ecosystem with hub structures, requiring collaboration and co-location. This ecosystem, characterized by shared investments, knowledge sharing, and collective problem solving, presents a significant departure from the current state.

The fourth 'retail as orchestrator' image envisions that retailers take proactive roles in collaboration with farmers and production partners to transform toward a resilient, self-sufficient and circular system. It marks a shift from prior studies of agriculture that emphasize local or regional optimization (e.g., Kuhmonen, 2017), by focusing also on the international aspects. While acknowledging the industry's strong dependency on international markets, it addresses local and regional production regarding food security, reliance on import and export, and sustainability and trade ethics regulations. It also highlights the unintended potential costs of altering production and consumption systems at other locations.

The fifth image of 'happy animals and healthy humans' emphasizes animal welfare and social sustainability as key drivers of sustainable transformation led by NGOs and other social organizations. It proposes the establishment of a Council of Animal Affairs as a key agent for change by regulating the welfare of animals and workers. Previous research underscores the importance of fairness in the food chain, reflecting animal welfare, labor, and farmers' inputs in pricing (Gomez-Limon, Gómez-Ramos, & Fernandez, 2009; Kuhmonen, 2017). Our fifth future image goes beyond such efforts by advocating for strong ethical regulations and highlighting both the benefits and drawbacks of using technology to enhance welfare. It also presents a shift in farmers' production, focusing either on high-welfare animal products or plant-based products using traditional practices.

The sixth image, 'living labs in the knowledge economy,' does not explicitly define sustainability but focuses on continuously advancing sustainable innovation. Giaoutzi, Stratigea, Van Leeuwen, and Nijkamp (2012) also highlighted the importance of advances in science and technology. Our findings emphasize these advances, but also focus on agentic action through collaborative efforts among farmers, producers, suppliers, and retailers as living lab partners supported by regulators, investors, and research institutes. While the poultry industry would remain highly dependent on global trade, it goes beyond merely trading products to develop adaptable production and consumption systems that can be exported to foreign locations.

These future images illustrate a rich set of sources and directions for agentic action in the Dutch poultry industry, expanding the opportunity space for sustainable transformation in its production and consumption systems. As such, our study highlights endogenous opportunities for system change which exploit internal competences and developments, rather than merely respond to external imperatives, as is commonly done in agricultural foresight exercises (Bourgeois & Sette, 2017).

6.2. Visualization of future images

Another key finding from this study is that visualization strengthens the role of future images as design tools that support the expansion of the opportunity space for innovation. Visualization provides a powerful illustration of the complexity of sustainability transformation and systemic innovation (Beers et al., 2010). Our results suggest that visualizing the impact on alternative socio-technical contexts can provide a more nuanced understanding of the drivers of change (in any specific future image). For instance, the 'changing globalized infrastructure related to import and export' driver takes on different meanings in images three, four, and six. Image three emphasizes local production and resource use; while image four pertains to how retailers balance resources and consumption patterns at local, regional, and international levels; image six focuses on developing adaptable local systems with niche

markets and the export of knowledge. Visualizing thus appears to concretize the various drivers of change within the context of a specific future image, giving them distinct meanings in that context.

Additionally, we found that visualization prompted decision making on what constitutes the 'foreground' and 'background' of an image. While each image has many dimensions, not all drivers of change can equally impact the future state. For instance, in the visualization of the second image, the niche markets, changing role of farmers, and their increased contact with consumers are highlighted as primary drivers of change and are therefore in the foreground of Fig. 4. The background in this drawing is formed by secondary drivers, such as changing policy from target to means-directed. Thus, the visual creator must judge which drivers of change constitute the foreground of the future state and which drivers are assumed to support the foreground changes.

6.3. Limitations and research agenda

For one, this study highlights how system change can arise from creating future images that enlarge the opportunity space. But we did not collect data on how decision-makers actually use this space. Follow-up studies should therefore explore how industrial actors use future images to reflect on opportunities for innovation and decide about moving ahead.

Second, the future images in this study represent possible socio-technical contexts that provide distinct opportunities for reconfiguring the production and consumption system of the Dutch poultry industry. With the aim to stimulate innovation, we focused on positive contexts for sustainability, rather than depicting failures in social, environmental or financial sustainability or predicting a collapse (De Smedt et al., 2013). Therefore, this study emphasizes the pivotal role of future images that focus on how the industry's production and consumption system can be designed for sustainable transformation. Other work in this area may target different types of futures exercises, informed by other aims.

Finally, different studies at other moments in time might result in other future images; the images created in this study are therefore not the only possible alternatives. In this study, we sought to mitigate these concerns by drawing on experts with diverse perspectives as well as minimizing interview biases. However, sustainability transformation is not only context-bound but also evolves over time, which implies future images targeting sustainability have to be frequently updated.

7. Conclusion

Sustainability pressures in agricultural industries call for reconfiguring production and consumption systems. However, mature industries have great difficulties in envisioning alternatives beyond product and service innovation. Diverse path dependencies, sustainability conceptualizations, and sources of agency contribute to different pathways toward systemic innovation. Our study demonstrates how future images can expand the opportunity space for sustainable transformation by envisioning alternative socio-technical settings. Future images and their visualization can aid sustainability transformation by concretizing drivers of change, supporting nuances in sense-making, and providing vivid yet flexible depictions that enable discussion. As with any futures exercise, these images represent one possible set of alternatives and should be frequently updated, also in view of the evolving nature of sustainability demands.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Georges Romme: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Arjan Markus:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Rianne Valkenburg:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Britt Smulders:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful for the research assistance of Loes Teunis. Further, the authors would like to thank the Poultry Expertise Center and AERES hogeschool for sharing their extensive knowledge about the Dutch poultry industry. The authors also acknowledge support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No. 101000216 - Code Refarm (Consumer driven demands to reframe farming systems). The research was conducted independently and reflects the authors own analysis and interpretation.

Appendix

Interview guideline

For each of the dimensions of the socio-technical context, repeat the following. First, provide the definition of the dimension.

Secondly, show the key trends as probes, while clearly stating that participants are not required to choose any or may discuss multiple ones. The visual template can be used for this, to give a reference point to the participant during the discussion (see Fig. A1). Then ask the following two questions while continually asking for clarification:

- i) which, if any, of these trends relates most closely to the future of the industry from your perspective as an expert, and
- ii) considering this trend as a force of change, can you specify how you think (hope, desire, or fear) it can impact the industry?

At the end of every interview, ask the participant if s/he has any remaining thoughts that were not discussed.

Future trends in the sector: the impact of global trends on the sector

An approach to understand how global trends influence the future of the sector. What will the sector look like in 2050 if these trends continue?

Name:

Role in ecosystem:

Fig. A1. Visual template used during interviews as reference point.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.futures.2024.103519](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2024.103519).

References

Adner, R. (2017). Ecosystem as structure: An actionable construct for strategy. *Journal of Management*, 43(1), 39–58.

Artuso, F., & Guijt, I. (2020). *Global Megatrends: Mapping the forces that affect us all*. Oxfam. (<https://policy-practice.oxfam.org/resources/global-megatrends-mapping-the-forces-that-affect-us-all-620942/>).

Augustine, G., Soderstrom, S., Milner, D., & Weber, K. (2019). Constructing a distant future: Imaginaries in geoeconomics. *Academy of Management Journal*, 62(6), 1930–1960.

Beers, P. J., Veldkamp, A., Hermans, F., van Apeldoorn, D., Vervoort, J. M., & Kok, K. (2010). Future sustainability and images. *Futures*, 42(7), 723–732.

Beldman, A., Benuis, M., ten Brummelhuis, A., Ellen, H., Hoste, R., van Horne, P., de Koning, K., & Vermeer, H. (2022). Op Weg naar een Duurzamere Veehouderij: Maatregelen en Stimulansen in de Melkvee-, Varkens- en Pluimveehouderij van 1980 tot 2020 (Wageningen Economic Research rapport; nr. 2022-012). Wageningen, Netherlands: Wageningen Economic Research.

Bell, W., & Mau, J. A. (1971). Images of the future: Theory and research strategies. In W. Bell (Ed.), *The sociology of the future* (pp. 6–44). New York: Russell Sage.

Berntsen, P., Menkveld, N., & Leguijt, M. (2021). *Visie op Pluimvee: Transitie in de Pluimveehouderij - Consument Maakt Draai naar Dierenwelzijn*. ABN Amro. Retrieved from (https://www.abnamro.nl/nl/media/rapport-visie-op-pluimvee_tcm116-116992.pdf).

Bourgeois, R., & Sette, C. (2017). The state of foresight in food and agriculture: Challenges for impact and participation. *Futures*, 93, 115–131.

De Olde, E. M., Linden, A. van der, Bolhaar, L. D., & Boer, I. J. M. de (2020). Sustainability challenges and innovations in the Dutch egg sector. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 258, Article 120974.

- De Smedt, P., Borch, K., & Fuller, T. (2013). Future scenarios to inspire innovation. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 80(3), 432–443.
- Dorninger, C., Abson, D. J., Apetrei, C. I., Derwort, P., Ives, C. D., Klanićki, K., Lam, D. P. M., Langsenlehner, M., Riechers, M., Spittler, N., & von Wehrden, H. (2020). Leverage points for sustainability transformation: A review on interventions in food and energy systems. *Ecological Economics*, 171, Article 106570.
- European Environment Agency. (2015). *The European Environment State and Outlook 2015: Assessment of Global Megatrends*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union (Retrieved from) (https://www.eea.europa.eu/soer/2015/global/action-download-pdf/at_download/file).
- Emirbayer, M., & Mische, A. (1998). What is agency? *American Journal of Sociology*, 103(4), 962–1023.
- European Commission. (2019). *EU Agricultural Outlook for Markets and Income, 2019–2030*. Brussels: European Commission, DG Agriculture and Rural Development (Retrieved from) (<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9ab90590-a676-11ea-bb7a-01aa75ed71a1>).
- European Commission. (2020). *Farm to fork strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system*. Retrieved from (https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/472acca8-7f7b-4171-98b0-ed76720d68d3_en?filename=f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf).
- European Commission. (2024a). *DG Agri Dashboard: Poultry Meat Broiler*. Retrieved September 27, 2024, from (https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/document/download/0ce25b9f-1571-4310-8531-3fe3346c49e0_nl?filename=poultry-meat-dashboard_en.pdf).
- European Commission. (2024b). *DG Agri Dashboard: Eggs Market Situation*. Retrieved September 27, 2024, from (https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/document/download/9bdf9842-1eb6-41a2-8845-49738b812b2b_en?filename=eggs-dashboard_en.pdf&prefLang=nl).
- Finn, E., & Wylie, R. (2021). Collaborative imagination: A methodological approach. *Futures*, 132, Article 102788.
- Garnett, K., Delgado, J., Lickorish, F. A., Pollard, S. J., Medina-Vaya, A., Magan, N., Leinster, P., & Terry, L. A. (2023). Future foods: Morphological scenarios to explore changes in the UK food system with implications for food safety across the food chain. *Futures*, 149, Article 103140.
- Garud, R., Kumaraswamy, A., & Karnøe, P. (2010). Path dependence or path creation? *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(4), 760–774.
- Geels, F. W. (2002). Technological transitions as evolutionary reconfiguration processes: A multi-level perspective and a case-study. *Research Policy*, 31(8–9), 1257–1274.
- Giaoutzi, M., Stratigea, A., Van Leeuwen, E., & Nijkamp, P. (2012). Scenario analysis as a foresight tool in agriculture. *International Journal of Foresight and Innovation Policy*, 8(2–3), 105–128.
- Gomez-Limon, J. A., Gómez-Ramos, A., & Fernandez, G. S. (2009). Foresight analysis of agricultural sector at regional level. *Futures*, 41(5), 313–324.
- Hin, K.-J., Wagenaar, J.P., Van der Zijpp, A., & Van der Weijden, W.J. (2013). *Kip: Het Meest Complexe Stukje Vlees - Marktmechanismen, Ketenrelaties en Integrale Duurzaamheid*. Wenschappelijke Raad voor Integrale Duurzame Landbouw en Voeding. (<https://edepot.wur.nl/286358>).
- Hörisch, J. (2018). How business actors can contribute to sustainability transitions: A case study on the ongoing animal welfare transition in the German egg industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 201, 1155–1165.
- Jarva, V. (2014). Introduction to narrative for futures studies. *Journal of Futures Studies*, 18(3), 5–26.
- Jing, R., & Benner, M. (2016). Institutional regime, opportunity space and organizational path constitution: Case studies of the conversion of military firms in China. *Journal of Management Studies*, 53(4), 552–579.
- Jokinen, L., Mäkelä, M., Heikkilä, K., Apostol, O., Kalliomäki, H., & Saarni, J. (2022). Creating futures images for sustainable cruise ships: Insights on collaborative foresight for sustainability enhancement. *Futures*, 135, Article 102873.
- Klein, F., Bansal, M., & Wohlers, J. (2017). *Beyond the noise: The megatrends of tomorrow's world*. Munich, Germany: Deloitte Consulting GmbH.
- Ko, B. K., & Yang, J. S. (2023). Developments and challenges of foresight evaluation: Review of the past 30 years of research. *Futures*, Article 103291.
- Kornish, L. J., & Ulrich, K. T. (2011). Opportunity spaces in innovation: Empirical analysis of large samples of ideas. *Management Science*, 57(1), 107–128.
- Kuhmonen, T., & Kuhmonen, I. (2015). Rural futures in developed economies: The case of Finland. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 101, 366–374.
- Kuhmonen, T. (2017). Exposing the attractors of evolving complex adaptive systems by utilising futures images: Milestones of the food sustainability journey. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 114, 214–225.
- Luoma, P., Penttinen, E., Tapio, P., & Toppinen, A. (2022). Future images of data in circular economy for textiles. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 182, Article 121859.
- Mäkelä, M., Parkkinen, M., Lyytimäki, J., & Nygrén, N. A. (2020). Futures images of woodchips as an energy source in Finland. *Futures*, 121, Article 102571.
- Marjamaa, M., & Mäkelä, M. (2022). Images of the future for a circular economy: The case of Finland. *Futures*, 141, Article 102985.
- Mauksch, S., von der Gracht, H. A., & Gordon, T. J. (2020). Who is an expert for foresight? A review of identification methods. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 154.
- Midgley, G., & Lindhult, E. (2021). A systems perspective on systemic innovation. *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 38(5), 635–670.
- Minkinen, M., Aufermann, B., & Ahokas, I. (2019). Six foresight frames: Classifying policy foresight processes in foresight systems according to perceived unpredictability and pursued change. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 149, Article 119753.
- Mische, A. (2009). Projects and possibilities: Researching futures in action. *Sociological Forum*, 24(3), 694–704.
- Mollenhorst, H., & De Boer, I. J. M. (2004). Identifying sustainability issues using participatory SWOT analysis: A case study of egg production in the Netherlands. *Outlook on Agriculture*, 33(4), 267–276.
- Nederlandse Vakbond Pluimveehouders (NVP) & LTO Nederland. (2023). *Sectorplan Aanpak van de Pluimveesector voor Reductie van de Emissie van Fijnstof (PM10)*. Retrieved September 28, 2024, from (<https://www.tweedekamer.nl/downloads/document?id=2023D04128>).
- Nygrén, N. A., Tapio, P., & Qi, Y. (2017). Lake management in 2030—Five future images based on an international Delphi study. *Futures*, 93, 1–13.
- Prager, S. D., & Wiebe, K. (2021). Strategic foresight for agriculture: Past ghosts, present challenges, and future opportunities. *Global Food Security*, 28, Article 100489.
- Rohrbeck, R., & Gemünden, H. G. (2011). Corporate foresight: Its three roles in enhancing the innovation capacity of a firm. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 78(2), 231–243.
- Rubin, A. (2013). Hidden, inconsistent, and influential: Images of the future in changing times. *Futures*, 45, S38–S44.
- Saritas, O., & Smith, J. E. (2011). The big picture—trends, drivers, wild cards, discontinuities and weak signals. *Futures*, 43(3), 292–312.
- Sarpong, D., Maclean, M., & Alexander, E. (2013). Organizing strategic foresight: A contextual practice of 'way finding'. *Futures*, 53, 33–41.
- Schwartz, P. (1996). *The art of the long view*. New York, NY: Doubleday.
- Shaaban, M., Voglhuber-Slavinsky, A., Dönitz, E., Macpherson, J., Paul, C., Mouratiadou, I., Helming, I., & Pierr, A. (2023). Understanding the future and evolution of agri-food systems: A combination of qualitative scenarios with agent-based modelling. *Futures*, 149, Article 103141.
- Spaniol, M. J., & Rowland, N. J. (2022). Business ecosystems and the view from the future: The use of corporate foresight by stakeholders of the Ro-Ro shipping ecosystem in the Baltic Sea Region. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 184, Article 121966.
- Spoelstra, S. F., Groot Koerkamp, P. W. G., Bos, A. P., Elzen, B., & Leenstra, F. R. (2013). Innovation for sustainable egg production: Realigning production with societal demands in The Netherlands. *World's Poultry Science Journal*, 69(2), 279–298.
- Sundbo, J. (2016). Food scenarios 2025: Drivers of change between global and regional. *Futures*, 83, 75–87.
- Truffer, B., Voß, J. P., & Konrad, K. (2008). Mapping expectations for system transformations: Lessons from sustainability foresight in German utility sectors. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 75(9), 1360–1372.
- Tsoukas, H., & Shepherd, J. (2004). Organisations and the future: From forecasting to foresight. *Management Today*, 20(7), 18–23.
- Vinnari, M., & Tapio, P. (2009). Future images of meat consumption in 2030. *Futures*, 41(5), 269–278.
- Weick, K. E. (1989). Theory construction as disciplined imagination. *Academy of Management Review*, 14(4), 516–531.
- Zanders, R. (2015). *Een Gezonde Pluimveehouderij: Het Kan Zo Mooi Zijn*. Dronen: CAH Vilentum.